

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

ISSN: 3030-3001

Том 1, Выпуск 3, 30 Ноября

CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGY CHARACTERISTICS OF MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS

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Abstract: Multiple sclerosis is one of the nephrological diseases that cause early disability. To date, the causes of this disease have not been determined. However, it is recognized by scientists that autoimmune processes, viruses, genetic predisposition, exposure to toxic products, and certain geographical conditions can be associated with multiple sclerosis.

Keywords: Multiple Sclerosis Origin, Causes, Origin, Causes of Disease Development, Treatment

Background: Multiple sclerosis is a disease of the central nervous system, which occurs due to the destruction of the myelin sheath of nerve fibers in the brain and spinal cord. This disease has an autoimmune origin, which means that the immune system mistakenly attacks and destroys its own tissues and organs.

According to the latest data, more than 3 million patients in the world have multiple sclerosis. But there is a big difference in the spread of the disease between different regions. Currently, as a result of the analysis of the epidemiology of multiple sclerosis, 3 zones have been identified around the world. The first is a zone where the disease is very common. This includes Europe and the north of the USA, Canada and the south of Australia, Russia and New Zealand. In these countries, there are more than 50 cases of multiple sclerosis per 100,000 people. The second - the disease occurs in 10-50 people out of 100,000 people, including Southern Europe, the South of the USA, and North Africa. The third zone includes regions where the disease is very rare - Asia, South America and South Africa (less than 10 per 100,000 population). Uzbekistan is among these regions. According to the reports received from the republican neurologists, the disease is almost not observed in our local population.

Many factors cause the disease. First of all, this is a weather factor, the disease is more common in cold and humid places. Secondly, there is a lack of certain fatty acids in food in these regions. Third - hereditary factors. If there is one patient in the family, the increase of the disease in this generation is more than 10-15 percent. The fourth is an infectious factor. There is also information that viruses play a role in the origin of the disease. This includes measles, herpes and other viruses. But there is still no certainty about this. Recent studies have shown that some inter-ethnic immunogenetic factors are of great importance in the origin of multiple sclerosis.

The new method of treatment includes several stages. First, doctors "destroy" the patient's immune system with the chemotherapy used to treat cancer. Secondly, the patient's immune system is "reloaded" with the help of the stem cell implant. This leads to the disappearance of the symptoms of multiple sclerosis in the patient, and the cessation of the progression of the disease.

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Conclusion: In conclusion, clinical neurology is a very broad and rapidly developing field. Neurological scientists are achieving positive results in the treatment of many diseases. We hope that new effective methods will be created and put into practice in the treatment of multiple sclerosis.

References:

1. <https://avitsenna.uz/tarqoq-skleroz-kasalligi/>
2. <https://uzbaza.uz/tarqoq-skleroz-kasalligi-va-davolash/>
3. <https://kun.uz/uz/news/2018/03/20/olimlar-tarkok-sklerozni-davolasning-angi-usulini-kasf-kilisdi>